

Appendix 5. CAMELOT guidance

Please cite this guidance as

Munthe-Kaas H, Booth A, Sommer I, Cooper S, Garside R, Hannes K, Noyes J and The CAMELOT Development Group. Developing CAMELOT for assessing methodological limitations of qualitative research for inclusion in qualitative evidence syntheses. *Cochrane Evidence Synthesis and Methods* 2024

CAMELOT

The CAMELOT approach is a method for making an assessment of the methodological strengths and limitations of primary qualitative research studies that are included in a qualitative evidence synthesis. Review authors make an assessment by identifying any concerns regarding the methods used in the study and considering the appropriateness of the fit between the meta and methods domains.

The four *Meta domains* (Research aim & question(s), Researchers, Stakeholders, Context) encourage review authors to consider characteristics of the primary study that are beyond how the study is carried out but inform the conduct and design of the study. The eight *Method domains* (Research strategy, Ethical considerations, Equity, diversity / inclusion considerations, Theory, Participant recruitment & selection, Data collection, Analysis and interpretation, Presentation of findings) encourage review authors to consider how the study was designed, planned and/or conducted.

Identification of concerns and assessments of appropriateness of fit are subjective judgements and depend on the review authors' experience and background. The assessments may be different between authors or review teams, and that is why it is important to include explanations for the sake of transparency.

Overview of CAMELOT domains

Contents

Instructions	5
Step 1: Data extraction/coding	5
Step 2: Concerns for each domain	5
Step 3: Appropriateness of fit between domains	5
Step 4: Overall assessment of fit	6
Step 5: Methodological limitations across primary studies in a review	6

Camelot primary study table	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Overview of domains	8
1 Research aim & question(s)	8
2 Stakeholders.....	9
3 Researchers.....	10
4 Context.....	10
5 Research approach.....	11
6 Ethical considerations	12
7 Equity, diversity & inclusion considerations	13
8 Theory	14
9 Participant recruitment & selection.....	15
10 Data collection	16
11 Analysis & interpretation	16
12 Presentation of findings	17
References	20

Step 1. Extract/code data

Extract or code data from the primary study related to the following domains (some of these domains will not be relevant for some studies):

Meta domains

1. Research aim & question(s)
2. Stakeholders
3. Researchers
4. Context

Method domains

Research design

5. Research strategy
6. Theory
7. Ethical considerations
8. Equity, diversity & inclusion consideration

Research conduct

9. Participant recruitment & selection
10. Data collection
11. Analysis and interpretation
12. Presentation of findings

See below for definitions of the CAMELOT domains

Step 2. Note any comments regarding each domain. This may include problems or missing information. This step is optional but will act as an audit trail and help to inform the subsequent steps.

Step 3. Describe concerns regarding, and make assessment of, fit between domains

- Describe concerns regarding appropriateness of fit between the Research design domains and each of the Meta domains and the Research conduct domains (as a whole). Make an assessment using the following categories to describe the fit: Excellent, Good, Fair, Poor, Unclear
- Describe concerns regarding appropriateness of fit between the Research conduct domains fit with each of the Meta domains. Make an assessment using the following categories to describe the fit: Excellent, Good, Fair, Poor, Unclear.

Step 4. Describe level of concern regarding methodological limitations

Combine these assessments to make an overall assessment of methodological limitations by indicating level of concern using the following categories and provide an explanation for your assessment:

- *No or minimal concerns, minor concerns, moderate concerns, serious concerns*

Step 5. Combine assessments across studies

Combine assessments of fit across studies contributing to a review finding and indicate level of concern regarding methodological limitations using the following categories:

- *No or minimal concerns, minor concerns, moderate concerns, serious concerns*

Instructions

Step 1: Data extraction/coding

- Extract or code data for each of the 12 CAMELOT domains.
 - This does not have to be an extra stage of the review process. It can be potentially be done during the data extraction stage of a QES.
 - Many CAMELOT domains are already included in a standard data extraction form (e.g., Research aim & question(s), participant recruitment and selection, data collection, analysis and interpretation).
- The definitions for each domain are provided below and describe the type of information that you may be looking for under each domain.
 - Note that it will not always be appropriate for review authors to extract/code data for all of the domains or all of the points under a domain.
- Use “N/A” if no data is extracted or coded for one or more of the CAMELOT domains and provide a rationale.
- Extracted or coded data is always related to the QES question. Another review team with a different review question may focus on different domains or highlight different concerns.
- Tips relevant to each domain (examples of data extraction and where to find information) are provided under domain definitions below.
- A CAMELOT primary study table (see example below) is provided to guide your assessment. Review authors can also incorporate the domains into their own data extraction template (CAMELOT study table: “Data”).

12 CAMELOT domains – link to domains

Meta domains

1. [Research aim & question\(s\)](#)
2. [Stakeholders](#)
3. [Researchers](#)
4. [Context](#)

Method domains

Research design

5. [Research strategy](#)
6. [Theory](#)
7. [Ethical considerations](#)
8. [Equity, diversity & inclusion consideration](#)

Research conduct

9. [Participant recruitment & selection](#)
10. [Data collection](#)
11. [Analysis and interpretation](#)
12. [Presentation of findings](#)

Step 2: Optional comments for each domain

- Make notes for each domain indicating any concerns, including where information is unclear or missing (see CAMELOT study table: “Optional comments”). Note that this step is optional, but is helpful for informing subsequent steps.

Step 3: Describing concerns regarding appropriateness of fit between domains

- For Research design domains, use “Optional comments” for each of the four underlying domains (Research strategy, ethical considerations, Equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations, Theory) to help describe any concerns regarding the appropriateness of fit between Research design domains and each of the four Meta domains as well as Research conduct domains as a whole. Indicate your concerns regarding appropriateness of fit using the following categories in the table:
 - No or minimal concerns
 - Minor concerns
 - Moderate concerns
 - Serious concerns
 - Unclear

- For Research conduct domains, use “Optional comments” for each of the four underlying domains (Participant recruitment and selection, Data collection, Analysis and interpretation, Presentation of findings) to help assessment describe any concerns regarding the appropriateness of fit between Research design domains and each of the four Meta domains. Indicate your concerns regarding appropriateness of fit using the following categories in the table:
 - No or minimal concerns
 - Minor concerns
 - Moderate concerns
 - Serious concerns
 - Unclear

Step 4: Overall assessment of methodological limitations

In the last row, make an overall assessment of concerns regarding methodological limitations for the study using the following categories: No or minimal, minor, moderate, or serious concerns and provide an explanation for the assessment. See below for a guidance on how to translate assessments of fit to levels of concern.

Level of concerns	Explanation
No or minimal concerns	None needed
Minor concerns	Summarize concerns regarding fit
Moderate concerns	Summarize concerns regarding fit
Serious concerns	Summarize concerns regarding fit
Serious concerns	Summarize concerns regarding fit

Step 5: Methodological limitations across primary studies in a QES to support GRADE-CERQual *methodological limitations* component

- For each synthesized qualitative finding, combine the description of concerns and assessments regarding fit
- between domains in a Table (see example below).

Review finding									
Describe if you have any concerns about fit, and indicate concerns regarding appropriateness of fit between:	Research design domains and Research aim & question(s)	Research design domains and Stakeholders	Research design domains and Researchers	Research design domains and Context	Research conduct domains and Research aim & question(s)	Research conduct domains and Stakeholders	Research conduct domains and Researchers	Research conduct domains and Context	Research design domains and Research conduct domains
Study ID 1	E.g., Serious concerns								
	Explanation								
Study ID 2	E.g., Moderate concerns								
	Explanation								
Study ID 3	E.g. No or minimal concerns								
	Explanation								

- Use the above Table to inform and support GRADE-CERQual methodological limitations component assessment.

Overview of domains

Of note, data of interest may be found anywhere in the paper, including the abstract, summary points, main body, tables, infographics and supplemental online files. It is also possible to contact the study authors for additional information and clarifications.

1 Research aim & question(s)

Definition: The purpose of the study and/or what questions the researchers intend to explore.

What to do: Consider the research aim & question(s) and describe (when possible):

- The research aim, the rationale for the research aim and how the aim relates to existing research.
- The research question, the clarity of the research question, and how the research question(s) was/were formed.

Note that some researchers may only state the research question and not the research aim/objective or vice versa depending on the approach used in the study. This does not necessarily constitute a concern.

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Abstract, Introduction or Methods sections of the study report.
- In mixed-methods studies where the qualitative research is one part of the study, consider the Research aim or question(s) related to the qualitative research only. Likewise, in studies where there are multiple research question(s), consider those most relevant for your review question.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Research aim & question(s)	The aim of the research project is to explore the difficulties encountered by social workers when assisting adult individuals without homes. To fulfill this purpose, the following goals were set: • To outline policy and laws related to homelessness in a context of a country in the Southern Hemisphere and to characterize homelessness on a worldwide scale. • To detail the assistance offered and obstacles encountered by social workers engaging with adult individuals lacking homes, supported by the ecological viewpoint. • To concretely examine the hurdles social workers encounter in providing services to adult individuals without homes. • To offer conclusions and suggestions derived from the research findings.	Adequate description of aims and objectives.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Research aim & question(s)	We investigated the reasons for participating in an HIV Vaccine Study through comprehensive qualitative discussions – examining the extent to which subjects view altruism, individual advantages, and financial incentives as driving factors.	

2 Stakeholders

Definition: Anyone with an interest (financial or otherwise) in the findings of the research study. Stakeholders are not the same as participants in this context. Stakeholders include patient and public participants.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- Whether and how stakeholders were involved in the design, planning, conduct, analysis or interpretation of the study findings
- The type of stakeholders or stakeholder groups (including funders), how they were recruited/selected, who they represent, their relationship to the research question and whether their conflicts of interest have been considered (if relevant).
- How the study was funded and the role of the funding

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

When possible, note where there are important problems with the description, for example if key stakeholder groups have been overlooked or if there was no involvement of any kind with important stakeholders.

*The term “stakeholders” may be not appropriate in all contexts

Tips:

- It is not always appropriate or necessary for stakeholders to be involved in the design or conduct of a study. This can depend on the review question, but stakeholder involvement is generally considered to have positive impacts on making the review more relevant.
- This information may be found in the Introduction, Methods, Discussion, Declarations or Acknowledgements sections of the study report.
- Note that stakeholder involvement is a relatively new practice and/or evolving in some disciplines and unlikely to be present in some studies.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Stakeholders	This study received funding from a central grant by the National Institute of Mental Health to the Center for Clinical and Behavioral Research on [Disease] at a noted Psychiatric Institute and a renowned University (nr. XXX); Lead Researcher, Ph.D.) and through an educational grant from the National Institute of Mental Health (nr. YYY, Behavioral Sciences Study on [Disease]; Lead Researcher, Ph.D.) The content herein is entirely attributed to the authors and may not reflect the official stance of the NIMH or the NIH.	No information on stakeholder involvement. Funders were not involved in research. Stakeholders input on the interview guide could have been helpful.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Stakeholders	Stakeholders representing patient groups were involved in the recruitment of participants, the development of the interview guide and the data collection.	Stakeholders involved, but their conflicts of interest not discussed. Also not discussed whether stakeholders had the skills/training to undertake data collection or their relationship to the participants.

3 Researchers

Definition: The investigators who have designed, planned and conducted the study and their relationship to the study question, context and/or participants.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some, or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- The researchers' role, their reflexivity including their relationship to (a) the research question, (b) research context and process, (c) any other decisions they make regarding methodology;
- The researchers' relationship to participants
- The researchers' background and/or epistemological stance, training, experience, affiliation;
- A discussion of how any of the above may influence the design and/or conduct of the study or the interpretation of the findings;
- A discussion of researcher actual or potential conflicts of interest (financial or otherwise).

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Introduction, Methods, Discussion or Declarations sections of the study report.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Researchers	The primary researcher, possessing prior expertise in qualitative study methodologies and having no conflicts of interest with the subjects, carried out all the interviews, starting with a broad inquiry, "Could you share the types of duties you've undertaken in clinical settings after earning a PhD in healthcare?"	No discussion of researchers' relationship to participants, context or research question. Short description of conflict of interest.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Researchers	The first authors is lead researcher with the Health & Gender Unit of a prominent Health Research Organization. They have a PhD in Health Sciences. The second author who oversees the Health & Gender Unit at the same research organization, is a MD. The third author's research focus is on gender-based violence, and adolescent health behaviours.	Authors describe their interest and professional background. They do not discuss their relationship to the participants or how their backgrounds could impact the design or conduct of the study or interpretation of the findings.

4 Context

Definition: The local, national or global context that the study was conducted in.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- The context in which the study was conducted, such as geography, climate, culture, when the study was conducted, and/or the legal, political, social, economic, healthcare or welfare systems.

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- Information about context may be found throughout the paper and in supplemental files (not just the Methods section)

- Consider that the contextual information could be considered at a global, national, subnational or local level.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Context	This research examines the experiences and expectations of parents in a high-income country in Europe regarding the tube feeding of children and proposes a method to enhance its management and communication.	Details regarding the setting and context of the study are absent: there is no description of where in the Netherlands the study was conducted, the healthcare setting in which participants received tube feeding, and the policy context or legal framework associated with tube feeding in children in the Netherlands. Detail about the population e.g. specific characteristics, perspectives or subgroups are also absent.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Context	The healthcare system in a European country operates under government ownership of public health facilities. All citizens of this country are entitled to healthcare services through a national statutory fund, known as the Health Insurance Institute (HII), which is supported by mandatory health insurance contributions (20%) and general taxation. Healthcare services are provided at no cost only to children, retirees, and individuals with disabilities. Working individuals are required to pay a premium to obtain a health insurance card...	No concerns

5 Research strategy

Definition: The overall intended plan, proposal or strategy for the study. This domain refers to the overarching roadmap for carrying out the research project (also referred to as research approach, study design, or type of study). This domain does not include issues related to participant recruitment and selection, data collection and analysis and interpretation. These are separate domains.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to some, any or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- The research strategy, including how the study was planned, designed and conducted.
- Availability or description of a research plan or protocol is available, any changes made to the original plan or protocol and rationale for changes
- The overarching methodologies (e.g., ethnography, phenomenology, etc.)
- Appropriate referencing to the methods used

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods, Data collection or Discussion sections of the study report, or in a separately published protocol.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Research strategy	In this study we used an ethnographic approach...The protocol is published online (DOI XXX). We intended on conducting interviews with 12 participants but were only able to make contact with 8 relevant participants.	Ethnographic approach with interviews. Reported changes from the original project plan.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Research strategy	We used participatory design methods to develop the XX tool.	Unclear what the researchers mean by participatory design methods (no reference or description of what this entails).

6 Ethical considerations

Definition: How the researchers considered and incorporated ethical principles and standards into decisions related to the design, planning and conduct of the study.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- Appropriate ethical approval
- Ethical issues in the design, planning, conduct, analysis, interpretation or dissemination of the study, selection, recruitment and informed consent of participants
- Discussion of how the study impacted the community, and how researchers considered issues related to maintaining respect and dignity of participants, and
- How the researchers addressed any issues related to ethics
- Data management and protection measures (e.g., data security and storage, etc.)

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods or Declarations sections of a study report, or in supplemental files. More details related to ethical considerations may also be found in the original ethical approval document when available, but it is generally not feasible to obtain additional documents.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Ethical considerations	In this community case analysis, there is no gathering of data from human subjects and no requirement for ethics clearance. The procedure was recorded with the oral agreement of all involved, and input on the document was requested, with special focus on incorporating the perspectives of participants from the faith-based groups...This community case analysis adhered to the principles of an internationally recognized declaration on ethical standards. Efforts were made to ensure participants' perspectives from the faith-based groups were included in the feedback on the document.	It is unclear how the researchers considered the impact of the study on the wider community and the relationship between the groups involved.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Ethical considerations	Before the interviews commenced, participants agreed to an Informed Consent Form (ICF), their answers were documented and transcribed, and the information underwent thematic examination... To distinguish the participants, the character P along with sequential numbers from one to 12 were employed at the conclusion of the quotes from the spoken replies...The research received clearance from the Ethics Board of a Federal University under No. 23081.011803/XXXX/XX, in accordance with the ethical and legal standards of a recognized resolution.	Adequate description of ethical considerations. No discussion of potential ethical issues.

7 Equity, diversity & inclusion considerations

Definition: Whether and how the researchers considered:

(1) equity – including distribution of power within the research context, whether there was equitable representation and participation in the research process, particularly for underrepresented groups, the possible differential experiences or perspectives of a phenomenon of interest for different populations and whether there was and whether unnecessary or discriminating differences in how people participate in a study

(2) diversity – including seeking out diverse experiences, perspectives and backgrounds, inclusion of participants with diverse backgrounds and considering how diversity can influence research findings

(3) inclusion – including the degree to which the research environment was such that all participants felt welcome and valued, whether culturally sensitive and inclusive research methods and communication strategies were employed and whether research materials, locations and processes were accessible for all participants.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all (but not limited to) of the following:

- Equity, diversity and inclusion considerations, which could include, but is not limited to Place of Residence, Race/Ethnicity, Visa/Residency status, Occupation, Gender, Religion, Education, Socioeconomic Status, and Social Capital, and Plus represents additional categories such as Age, Disability, and Sexual Orientation (PROGRESS-Plus)^{1 2}. Review authors may consider using an existing framework or checklist to assess equity (e.g., CONSORT Equity extension³ PRISMA equity extension⁴)
- How the researchers addressed any issues related to equity, diversity and inclusion

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods, Participant characteristics tables, Findings, Discussion or Declarations section of a study report, or in supplementary files. Note that more detailed information has only recently become a standard requirement for many publishers. Furthermore, research and standards related to this domain are evolving and may include additional or fewer considerations for different disciplines and journals.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Equity, diversity and inclusion	We provided individuals who opted out of the project a choice to be interviewed via phone or email. These methods were chosen based on: recommendations from two engagement panels - a National Clinical Research Network's Mental Health Consumer Research Group and a Primary Healthcare Research Participation Initiative; insights from researchers experienced	Researchers used strategies to improve EDI – accessibility of interviews and decreasing burden of participation. Sampled to maximize variation. Did not address issues related to socio-

	with similar populations; studies indicating that those declining participation might prefer not to engage in in-person discussions; and findings that carefully conducted phone and email interviews can collect comparable information to in-person conversations... and facilitate engagement with 'remote, widely spread, or marginalized groups that are frequently neglected or overlooked'... Initially, we selected 20 interview participants to ensure a wide range of differences in characteristics such as age, sex, and location... To reduce the burden on participants, transcripts were not shared with them for comments, nor were they requested to give feedback on the research findings.	economic status or minority or indigenous backgrounds.
--	---	--

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Equity, diversity and inclusion	The potential inclusion of practitioners from different studies was considered due to the evolving nature of [Smoking Cessation Programs] in a given country, which made finding appropriate participants especially difficult.	Participants age, gender and professional role reported. No discussion of strategies to seek diverse experiences. No discussion on power dynamics. No discussion on accessibility of interviews.

8 Theory

Definition: Organization of concepts, ideas, literature or principles into systems or frameworks that attempt to describe, explore, explain, understand or predict a phenomenon.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- Whether and how theory or a concept was used (appropriately and consistently) to inform the planning, design, and/or conduct of the study.
- Whether and how theory or a concept was used (appropriately and consistently) to analyze explore and/or contextualize the findings from the study.
- Whether and how a theoretical or conceptual framework was used. Theoretical or conceptual frameworks can be presented as logic models, theories of change, or conceptual model. Theory refers to a collection of concepts or ideas that are organized in a reasonable way to explain a phenomenon in the real world.
- If a theoretical or conceptual framework has not been used, is an appropriate rationale provided?

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Introduction, Methods, Findings, or Discussion sections of the study report and in supplementary files.
- Note that you may have included some of this information under “Research strategy” or “Analysis and interpretation”. In this case, be careful not to assess the same concerns twice.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Theory	The theoretical underpinning of this research was based on the Health Belief Model (HBM). Employing the HBM, it's posited that an individual is more inclined to participate in screening if they believe they are at risk for conditions like hypertension or diabetes, view these conditions as seriously impactful, and see screening as beneficial for preventing or managing these	Appropriate theory used consistently throughout project to informing interview guide to coding data to interpreting findings.

	illnesses. This framework guided our methods for gathering and analyzing data, specifically in the creation of the interview guide and the coding strategy. The interview guides can be found in Supplementary Material 2. Codes were developed by identifying key phrases that encapsulated the primary idea of statements related to the core research inquiry: what factors affect the decision to undergo screening and to act on that decision? After the research team independently reviewed the initial coding structures, the coding framework was updated to resolve discrepancies and organize codes into broader themes that illuminate the screening behaviors of the individuals served.	
--	--	--

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Theory	We used the Theoretical domains framework to explore teacher satisfaction with the learning resources...	The authors refer to the Theoretical domains framework without referencing it in the methods. There is no more mention of this framework in the findings or the conclusion. It is unclear how the theory was used.

9 Participant recruitment & selection

Definition: How participants were identified, recruited and selected for the research study.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- How and why participants were recruited and selected, and who was not recruited and selected
- Description of participants and non-participants
- Numbers and reasons for any participant refusal, dropout, who was not included or represented
- Any incentives provided for participation

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods, Findings, or Discussion section of the study report or in supplementary files.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Participant recruitment and selection	Health care workers	No discussion of recruitment or selection.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Participant recruitment and selection	We conducted 25key informant interviews in three countries, in winter 2016. We selected our informants to cover a range of perspectives.	Unclear what range of perspectives refers to. Unclear how participants were recruited.

10 Data collection

Definition: The process of gathering qualitative information (data) in the form of perspectives, experiences or opinions from participants, and/or observations, prolonged engagement in the field by researchers in order to explore or answer the research questions and address the research aim.

What to do: Extract relevant data for the review question from the primary study related to any, some or all of (but not limited to) the following:

- Rationale for data collection methods
- Development of data collection materials (e.g., interview guide development and testing)
- What type of data were collected (e.g., recorded interviews, structured observations, field notes, pictures, videos, photos, etc.)
- Data collection methods, including language used when engaging with participants, how long researchers were engaged with participants
- When data were collected, who was present during and physical setting of data collection, the medium through which data were collected (e.g., online or in-person or ethnographic fieldwork, etc.)

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods, Results, Findings or Discussion sections of the study report, or in supplementary files.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Data collection	We conducted five focus groups with 5 men who have sex with men in each group. We used a semi-structured conversation guide. We recorded and transcribed the discussions.	Unclear how the conversation guide was collected or why researchers chose focus groups instead of interviews (which seem more appropriate). The article is in English but the setting is a non-English country and unclear which language was used in the discussions or how translation was addressed. Unclear who facilitated the discussions.

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Data collection	We conducted two in-depth interviews with key informants.	Almost no information provided regarding data collection.

11 Analysis & interpretation

Definition: The process of systematically examining, exploring and interrogating data gathered during the study in order to identify themes, patterns, lines of argument and if appropriate theories and gain a greater understanding of the phenomenon of interest.

What to do: Extract data from the primary study related to all, some or any of (but not limited to) the following:

- Rationale for choice of analysis
- Analysis and interpretation methods, including plans for data analysis, deviations from the protocol, how analysis, interpretation and if appropriate theory development was conducted, who was involved in data analysis,

- Strategies to improve trustworthiness (e.g., methods of triangulation, participant feedback, multiple observations etc)
- Disconfirming findings and whether researchers challenged their findings
- Data saturation*
- Use of analysis software (including artificial intelligence software)

*This is a contested concept and may be interpreted according to different methods (e.g., information power)

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Methods, Findings, Results or Discussion sections of the study report, or in supplementary files.

Examples:

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Analysis & interpretation	<p>Audio recordings of discussions were transcribed and organized by groups: adolescents, guardians, and educators, with non-verbal cues included. Using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, the team identified and analysed patterns in the data, starting from familiarization, through open coding without preset codes, to pattern identification mainly at the semantic level. Patterns were continuously refined in a cyclical review process, ensuring they matched the entire dataset and aligned with the study's questions, culminating in defined, named patterns within a thematic structure that highlights socio-ecological interactions.</p> <p>To ensure reliability, two researchers coded all transcripts independently, resolving discrepancies through team discussions to identify key themes. Quotes were translated into English, emphasizing the analysis was conducted manually without software assistance, maintaining the study's clarity and integrity.</p>	No concerns

Study ID:	Data from primary study	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Analysis & interpretation	<p>Information from exit interviews was handled and evaluated using statistical software. ... Transcriptions from each research location were examined through content analysis techniques, with prevalent themes recorded by location. For this summary, the qualitative outcomes were translated and transcribed into English by the lead researcher and the research group.</p>	<p>Missing information regarding analysis methods (who conducted it, steps taken, coding, etc.). Evidence of disconfirming findings in the article. Authors don't discuss why they used statistical software for qualitative analysis</p>

12 Presentation of findings

Definition: How the findings from the study are organized and communicated and how well they represent the underpinning data.

What to do: Consider the study findings and describe (when possible):

- How closely the study findings represent the data (e.g., how categories and themes , lines of inquiry and theories and author interpretations are derived from the data)
- How clearly findings are articulated

- The adequate reflection of participants’ voices and participants’ meanings of experiences, perceptions (etc) and, where relevant, inclusion of other forms of supporting evidence (e.g. quotations from an interview, field note entries, etc.)

Note concerns and where important information is missing.

Tips:

- This information may be found in the Findings, Results, Discussion or Conclusion sections of the study reports, or in supplementary files.

Examples:

Study ID:	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Presentation of findings	Findings were presented clearly but the authors have lumped data under broad categories that bear only limited resemblance to themes from the interviews and which are so generic that they are almost non-informative. Within the categories they present a few isolated verbatim extracts without any interpretation and they have lists of individual cases which look like they are just trying to get as many respondents covered within a tight word limit.

Study ID:	Optional comments (notes to self, including any problems or missing information)
Presentation of findings	Findings in the main text do not match the findings presented in the abstract. Furthermore, the participants’ voices are not represented (e.g. quotes). The findings in the main text do not appear to address the objective of the paper.

Describing concerns regarding appropriateness of fit between domains

The following guidance is preliminary and subject to revision as more review teams apply CAMELOT and we have more examples to illustrate concerns regarding appropriateness of fit.

When describing concerns regarding the appropriateness of fit between domains, use notes from the “optional comments” section of the table. All relevant notes should be included in your description of concerns, however, just because you have identified problems or missing information for a domain, does not necessarily mean that this will constitute a concern regarding appropriateness of fit between domains.

See below for an overview of fictional examples illustrating possible concerns regarding fit between domains.

Concerns regarding fit	Research aim and/or question	Stakeholders	Researchers	Context	Research conduct
Research strategy	The research aims to explore adolescent pregnancy and education obtainment. The ethnographic	Community-based participatory research, but teenagers (main target group) not included in stakeholder group.	Ethnographic study, but researchers have family members in the community.	Ethnographic research during a pandemic with little access to personal protection equipment.	Researchers report using an ethnographic approach, but they collect data using open-ended survey questions,

	approach failed to consider that the phenomenon of interest happened long before the study took place.				
Ethical considerations	The aim of the research was to explore conflict between different community groups. Unclear whether the study authors considered the impact of the research on the local community.	Informed consent was not obtained from all stakeholders.	Researchers were doctors who sought sensitive information from a vulnerable population that they worked with and did not discuss their relationship to the participants.	Young people with problem behaviour were taken out of class to be interviewed.	Sensitive data was collected without obtaining informed consent.
Equity, diversity and inclusion considerations	Aim of the research is to explore use of maternal healthcare services and the researchers failed to include women from marginalized groups, or failed to ensure a research environment which was accessible for women with prams.	Homogenous group of stakeholders.	Researchers did not consider their background when interviewing participants from low socioeconomic settings.	The geographical setting of the study was not conducive to including participants from marginalized groups.	The authors declared saturation without adequately considering diverse perspectives.
Theory	Aim of the research is to explore teachers' satisfaction with new learning resources, and the researchers used the Theoretical domains framework (related to behaviour) which is appropriate.	Feminist theory was used to inform the data collection, but only men stakeholders were asked for input.	Researchers did not acknowledge their authorship and development of the theory used to interpret the findings.	The theory used to inform the study was developed within a high income country setting. It is unclear how it fits in a low-income country setting.	The theory used for framework analysis was inappropriate.

Concerns regarding fit	Research aim and/or question	Stakeholders	Researchers	Context
Participant recruitment and selection	Participants were men over 40 discussing sexual health among adolescents.	Stakeholders were not involved in identifying relevant participants. The participant pool in this case is very narrow and it would have been advantageous to have stakeholder input.	The researchers used convenience sampling without discussing the possible implications.	Participants were recruited to discuss a topic that was illegal in their setting. This was not discussed by the authors.
Data collection	The researchers used focus groups to collect data to address a sensitive topic.	Stakeholders conducted data collection but did not appear to receive any training prior to doing so.	The researchers conducted interviews in their own home without discussing implications.	The data was collected 20 years after participants experienced the phenomenon of interest.
Analysis & interpretation	The analysis methods were inappropriate to address the research question.	Funders were allowed to make comments on the findings before publication.	The researchers did not acknowledge their background as teachers and how they may have influenced how their interpretation of the findings.	The researchers failed to interpret the findings in light of the political context (face masks are a highly contested intervention in the context).

Presentation of findings	The findings did not address the aim of the research.	The findings were presented without checking with the community. Some of the findings were sensitive and may have negatively impacted community members.	The researchers did not acknowledge the impact of their actual conflicts of interest on the types of findings they chose to emphasize in the conclusion.	The findings were presented for only one of the contexts in the study.
---------------------------------	---	--	--	--

References

1. Oliver S, Kavanagh J, Caird J, et al. Health promotion, inequalities and young people's health: a systematic review of research. 2008
2. O'Neill J, Tabish H, Welch V, et al. Applying an equity lens to interventions: using PROGRESS ensures consideration of socially stratifying factors to illuminate inequities in health. *Journal of clinical epidemiology* 2014;67(1):56-64.
3. Welch VA, Norheim OF, Jull J, et al. CONSORT-Equity 2017 extension and elaboration for better reporting of health equity in randomised trials. *Bmj* 2017;359
4. Welch V, Petticrew M, Tugwell P, et al. PRISMA-Equity 2012 extension: reporting guidelines for systematic reviews with a focus on health equity. *PLoS medicine* 2012;9(10):e1001333.